

**DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF REPEATED FEEDING OF WORMS IN
SURKHANDARYA CLIMATIC CONDITIONS**

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Abstract: *In the conditions of climate, breed and and on behalf of the user Ushbu tour finishing articles about IP Surkhondar, however, we cannot repeat until mavsumlard, hususiyatlari kilingan bilib duraga pillalar bokilgan kur pillalaring research is posted here, heads of cities and districts, kobigi weight of silkworm cocoon, cocoons of raw materials and ip by ip uzun umumiy, however, we cannot.*

Keywords: Temperature, cocoon, shell, climate, season, drying, hot air, mulberry silkworm.

Methods. One of the main conditions for the development of the economy of our republic is the systematic increase in the quality of products. Improving the quality of products, expanding their assortment and meeting consumer demand are some of the important tasks of the current market economy. The quality of the products is guaranteed as a standard and a technical specialist for compliance with regulatory requirements. A number of practical work on the development of silk production is being carried out in our republic. Since 2017, silkworms have been bred in our Republic 2 times, and in 2022, silkworms have been bred 4 times, and SAWS have prepared more than 22 thousand tons of sawdust raw materials. There is no separate food base for summer-fed worms, since all mulberry leaves are eaten by worms that are fed in the brood (in the first season). Consequently, in the summer (repeated) feeding of worms, mulberries are used a second time, that is, branches from the trunk of a mulberry tree and the base of mulberry bushes are cut off, branches in the head are thinned out. The use of mulberries twice a year in the same way provides an opportunity to feed (repeatedly) 10-15% of the amount of worms in the brood compared to caught worms in the summer. But if more than 15% of the branches in the Mulberry head are cut off during repeated worm feeding, as well as the Leaf is prepared incorrectly, then the next year there may be a lack of leaves when feeding worms in the cocoon. Therefore, the correct distribution of the work of repeated weevil feeding between all brigades and werewolf zvenos, as well as the correct preparation of mulberry leaves in summer and autumn weevil feeding, has an enormous limescale. At the same time, as in any other city in the country, the area has many amenities and leisure facilities to help you relax and unwind in the hot and cool weather. In the summer and autumn seasons, the buildings where the worm is fed should be thick-walled, doors and windows should be densely blocked, with holes in the wall. At the same time near this building, there should be a ditch, a pond, the water of which is constantly flowing. For feeding in the summer period, breeds and hybrids are selected in which the worm can withstand summer heat and air dryness. In surkhandarya climatic conditions, Ipakchi-1, Ipakchi -2 and foreign Chinese hybrids tolerate well. Summer-fed worms are artificially exposed to worm eggs by exposure to chlorotic acid. 9-10 days after exposure of chloritic acid to the worm egg, the worm emerges from the egg. When hatching worms, which are fed in summer, the temperature is set at 24-26 degrees, the relative humidity of

the air is 70-80%. In the summer, it is not difficult to make the temperature of the incubator at this level, for this there is also no point in burning the stove of course. It is not so difficult to keep the temperature of the incubator and the relative humidity of the air at the appropriate level by using the coolness of the night, the heat of the daytime correctly and spraying water on the floor of the building. But this should not be forgotten that it is necessary to check the temperature of the interior of the building and air humidity more often around the clock, since the dryness of the summer heat and air can dry out the worm egg, as a result of which fewer cocoons can come out of them. All buildings where worms are fed in the summer are necessarily disinfected with a 4% Solution of formalin or monochloramine, regardless of whether the worms fed in the first season are sick or not. These buildings are disinfected even after the end of summer worm feeding so that the infection of the disease does not persist in the subsequent feeding worms.

The place for worms that are fed in the summer should be prepared in the following size. A box should be 2 square meters for worms of the first age, 5-8 square meters for the second age, 12-15 square meters for those of the second age, 30-35 square meters for the Fourth Age, 60-70 square meters for the fifth age. In summer worm feeding, the temperature of the wormhole (until the worm is introduced into it) is supplied to 28 degrees, and the relative humidity of its air is 50-55%. This heat and moisture will be stored until the worms reach the Third Age. The worm's temperature is 27 degrees Celsius at the third age, relative humidity is 50-60 %, Fourth-Age heat is 27 degrees Celsius, relative humidity is 55-60 %, fifth-age heat is 24 degrees Celsius, relative humidity is 65-75%, and peak-wrapping period heat is 21-23 degrees Celsius, relative humidity is 65-75%. It is necessary to attach special importance to the good quality of the leaves, which are made in the method of repeated cultivation of worms. Worms of the first and second age are fed with young leaves from bachki branches and branches that come out from the bottom of the Mulberry head. Worms of the third age are given small bachki branch leaves, worms of the fourth and fifth age are given large bachki branch leaves, as well as Horn leaves, which are cut by thinning the Mulberry Calla. In this case, the Mulberry branches cut thinly should not exceed 10-12% of the main branches in the head.

The leaves that are given to the worms daily are cut from 5 am to 10 am, and the leaves that are eaten at night are cut from 6 pm until the eyebrow darkens. The cut leaves are quickly transported to the leaves or to a cool cellar. Here, the top of the leaves is wrapped with a hopped sheet or tent. When rearing worms, yellow Wasps and brown wasps do a lot of damage, as these wasps transport silkworms and cause a decrease in Cocoon yield. When rearing worms, yellow Wasps and brown wasps do a lot of damage, as these wasps transport silkworms and cause a decrease in Cocoon yield. A fine-eyed wire mesh, gauze, or fine-perforated paper is caught against these wasps in wormhole Windows, Windows, and other ventilation holes. Old gannas are quickly burned along with worm droppings after the Ganna has been changed to prevent Wasps and other insects from coming to the rearing worms. Other procedure rules for repeated worm feeding do not differ from larval (first season) worm feeding procedures. In our research work, we aim to study the technological indicators of silkworm cocoons bred in repeated seasons, along with domestic breed hybrids, foreign breed and hybrid cocoons. Currently, in our country, almost 70-80% of silkworm seeds are imported from the people's Republic of China. Accordingly, in our research work, the worms obtained from The brought seed were fed at different temperatures in the spring and summer season. (Table 1).

In different seasons, the air temperature of the rooms where silkworms are raised by young

Table 1

№	Age of worms	In spring and summer, the air on the roof of the cottage burns at a temperature of °C			
		Spring	Spring	Summer	Summer
		Recommended	Fed	Recommended	Fed
1	first	26±2	26-27	26±2	28-32
2	second	26±2	26-27	26±2	29-33
3	third	24±2	24-23	24±2	30-31
4	fourth	24±2	24-26	24±2	31-33
5	fifth	24±2	24-26	24±2	33-34

We can see that the feeding conditions of silkworms bred in the spring season are fed under normal conditions, and the air temperature does not exceed the recommended norm.

In conclusion, the features of repeated worm feeding agrotechnics include:

-using mulberries in summer and autumn feeding to worms so that their leaf harvest next year does not decrease;

-making the temperature of the wormhole and the relative humidity of the air at the appropriate level;

-the use of roughened succulent leaves to increase the level of leaf spotting as well as to give to the worms by taking good care of the mulberries;

We can see that the air temperature of The Silkworm raised in the summer season rises sharply, and the conditions of feeding in the room are not well established.

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